

Leveraging YouTube as a Valuable Educational Resource for Library and Information Science students in Delta State University, Abraka

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Abstract

The study determined the extent to which Library and Information Studies (LIS) students are aware of and patronize/utilize YouTube as an educational resource. Two research questions and one hypothesis guided the study. A descriptive survey design was used by the researchers. The population of the study comprised 477 undergraduate students, of whom 217 were randomly selected. The questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The questionnaire was validated by two experts, and the Cronbach alpha was used to establish the reliability of the instrument, which yielded 0.75. Data were analyzed with frequency counts and simple percentages, and Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) version 23 was used to generate the mean and standard deviation, while Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 significant levels. The findings revealed that the undergraduates had a high extent of awareness and utilization of YouTube as an educational resource. Lastly, the test of hypothesis shows there is a significant relationship between LIS undergraduates' extent of awareness and utilization of YouTube as an educational resource at Delta State University, Abraka. Based on the findings, the researchers recommended promoting awareness, integrating YouTube educational content into the curriculum, fostering critical evaluation skills, facilitating collaboration with content creators, and establishing mechanisms for continuous assessment and feedback.

Keywords: YouTube, educational resource, undergraduates, library, and information science students

Introduction

The advent of information and communication technology (ICT) has indeed brought about significant transformations in various aspects of our lives, including the education sector. The integration of ICT into education has led to a revolution in traditional learning methods, with a shift towards e-learning modes and digital resources (Mansi et al., 2023; Varun, S., & Dharunya, 2023). This transformation has empowered students to access educational materials remotely, breaking the limitations of traditional classroom-based approaches. Education is no longer confined to the four walls of a classroom, as technology has made it possible to record and store

educational resources online, allowing easy access and retrieval regardless of one's location, which has impacted the use of print resources (Chohda & Kumar, 2023). Particularly noteworthy is the impact of digital platforms like YouTube, which have emerged as indispensable tools for accessing and disseminating educational content across diverse disciplines.

Alabi et al. (2020) defined YouTube as a video-sharing website where users can upload, share, and view video content. In this context, YouTube is an online platform that serves as a valuable resource for accessing educational content and supporting learning experiences. Burhandi & Alpan (2021) emphasize the role of YouTube in democratizing education by providing a platform where professionals and experts can share valuable content, fostering lifelong learning among students. They also highlight that YouTube is an interactive platform for learning, playing a significant role in encouraging lifelong learning among students. With the availability of multimedia tools, learning has become more accessible and engaging, and YouTube stands out as a primary platform for disseminating educational materials (Cholik et al., 2023). Not only does YouTube provide access to a wealth of educational videos, but it also facilitates interaction and knowledge sharing among students and educators. YouTube serves as an inspiring platform for students, encouraging active engagement through video-based learning.

YouTube offers a diverse range of educational videos covering various disciplines, such as tutorials, lectures, presentations, demonstrations, experiments, and educational documentaries (Srivastava, 2023). These videos serve as a valuable resource for students, teachers, and lifelong learners, providing them with a digital platform to explore and engage with educational materials. The content is created by educators, experts, institutions, and content creators who generously share their knowledge and expertise. Shoufan & Mohamed (2022) opined that the key advantages of YouTube in education is its extensive library of educational content, which complements traditional learning methods and offers valuable resources for teachers to enhance their teaching styles while keeping students engaged. The platform enables self-directed learning and provides flexibility in terms of when and where individuals choose to access educational content

YouTube promotes engagement and interactivity in the learning process by allowing interaction through commenting, liking, sharing, and subscribing to channels (Stanley & Zhang, 2018). This facilitates communication and collaboration among students, educators, and online communities. According to Shoufan & Mohamed (2022), YouTube provides features like playlists, recommended videos, and video responses, which help students discover related content and explore different perspectives on a topic. Despite its potential benefits, the researchers observed a notable underutilization of YouTube as an educational resource among Nigerian undergraduates. This may be due to limited awareness and their perceptions about the quality and relevance of available educational content. The optimal use of any educational resources is determined by the student's level of awareness and their perceptions about the quality of resources (Sawyer-George et al., 2022). Many students may not be able to locate them or even use them for their academic work if they are unaware of the educational content on YouTube. To address this gap, it is imperative to study library and information science (LIS) students who are future information

professionals. This research will provide valuable insights into their information behaviours, multimedia literacy, and readiness to leverage YouTube educational content and other open educational resources as future information professionals. This study, therefore, examines the extent to which LIS undergraduates are aware of and patronize/utilize YouTube as an educational resource at Delta State University, Abraka.

Statement of the Problem

YouTube is a digital platform that provides access to a wide range of educational videos in various disciplines. Despite the potential benefits YouTube offers as an educational resource, it is doubtful whether university students in Nigeria are fully aware of its educational potential. While YouTube has gained widespread adoption for academic purposes in many countries, there is limited documented evidence of its usage for educational purposes in Nigeria. Internationally, YouTube has become an integral part of higher education. For instance, in Jordan, a study by Sharayah et al. (2023) found that that 91% of medical students use YouTube for learning physical examination. Popular educational channels like Crash Course, Khan Academy, and TED-Ed have millions of subscribers globally, demonstrating the platform's educational reach (Akbari & Rochaety, 2023). These channels offer content across various disciplines, from science and mathematics to history and literature, attracting millions of views.

In contrast, studies conducted at various Nigerian universities, including the University of Abuja, University of Africa, Toru-Orua, and Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, reveal low levels of engagement with digital resources like online educational videos (Mohammed, 2023; Ogunbodede & Oribhabor, 2022; Igbinovia et al., 2022). This underutilization may be that most undergraduates are not fully aware of the relevance of YouTube as a valuable educational resource platform. The gap in YouTube low utilization for educational purposes in Nigeria raises concerns about information access and retrieval skills, multimedia literacy, and digital competencies of Nigerian undergraduate students.

Addressing these gaps necessitates a study of LIS undergraduates regarding the use of YouTube as an educational resource. Studying LIS students' engagement with YouTube as an educational resource is crucial as these future information professionals will play a pivotal role in shaping digital literacy, information behavior, and knowledge dissemination practices, while their insights can inform curriculum development and bridge the gap between traditional and digital resources in the evolving landscape of information access and use. This study, therefore, examines the extent to which LIS undergraduates are aware of and patronize/utilize YouTube as an educational resource at Delta State University, Abraka. By focusing on this specific institution, the research aims to provide insights into the awareness, and utilization of YouTube as an educational tool among Nigerian university students, potentially paving the way for broader studies and educational interventions across the country.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the extent to which Library and Science undergraduates at Delta State University are aware and utilize YouTube as academic resource platform. The specific objectives are:

- i. To ascertain the extent to which LIS undergraduates are aware of YouTube as an educational resource
- ii. To determine the extent to which LIS undergraduates utilize YouTube as an educational resource

Research Questions

The following questions will guide the study:

- i. To what extent are LIS undergraduates aware of YouTube as an educational resource?
- ii. To what extent do LIS undergraduates utilize YouTube as an educational resource?

Hypothesis

- i. There is no significant relationship between LIS undergraduate students' awareness and utilization of YouTube educational content

Literature Review

Three main principles serve as the framework for this literature review: students' awareness of YouTube as an educational resource, and students' utilization of YouTube as an educational resource.

Students' Awareness of YouTube as an Educational Resource

Okafor (2019) examined the awareness and usability of YouTube videos on undergraduates' interest in chemistry. The study made use of a quantitative survey research design which involved 180 samples. The results revealed that chemistry undergraduates have a favourable interest at medium awareness levels on YouTube videos which has led to a positive interest in chemistry. Similarly, Oteyola et al. (2019) investigated south-western Nigerian university undergraduates' acceptance of YouTube as a web-based instructional tool. The study employed the descriptive survey research design and the population consisted of all registered undergraduates in south-western Nigeria. The findings indicated that 58% of the undergraduates are moderately aware of YouTube as an instructional tool and that the undergraduates accept YouTube as a web-based instructional tool. Overall, both studies indicated that undergraduate students generally had an intermediate/moderate level of awareness regarding YouTube as a web-based instructional tool. These studies suggest that YouTube can be a valuable resource for educational purposes, with a significant proportion of students already aware of and accepting its use in learning.

Students' Utilization of YouTube as an Educational Resource

Abdullah (2018) explored the utilization of YouTube as an information resource to support university courses. The questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The collected data were analysed using frequency and simple percentages. The general results reveal that the use

of YouTube in the classroom influences student engagement. Similarly, Pradhan et al. (2024) conducted a study assessing the utilization and effectiveness of YouTube in Anatomy education among medical students. The study cohort comprised 195 medical students (average age: 19.8 ± 1.1 years), 62.6% females and 37.4% males. YouTube emerged as extensively utilized, with 94.5% of males and 96.7% of females reporting general usage and 91.8% of males and 89.3% of females utilizing it for medical studies. For human anatomy learning, 93.2% of males and 89.3% of females relied on YouTube. In a related study, Alvankan (2022) investigated the effect and impact of YouTube educational content on students' learning outcomes. The study sampled 200 students from Cohat University of Science and Technology. The result of the study indicated that students prefer YouTube for educational purposes and research. In conclusion, these studies collectively demonstrate the widespread utilization of YouTube as an information resource in various educational contexts. Both university students and medical students rely on YouTube for learning, with positive effects on student engagement and learning outcomes. YouTube serves as a preferred platform for accessing educational content and supporting academic studies.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised 477 undergraduate students out of which 217 were randomly selected. The Taro Yamane sample size formula was used to determine the sample size of the study. The questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. A total of 250 questionnaires were distributed to the respondents and 217 were retrieved and found usable. The response to each of the items was weighted on 4-points Likert-type scoring scale. The respondents were free to choose Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points, Agree (A) = 3 points, Disagree (D) = 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 point. From the scale, a criterion score of 2.5 was adopted. The criterion score was obtained as follows: Criterion score = $((4+3+2+1))/4 = 2.5$. For research questions 1 and 2, the response below 2.5 was adjudged as low-extent awareness and low-extent utilization, while the mean response of 2.5 and above was adjudged as high-extent awareness and high-extent utilization. Data were analysed with frequency count, and simple percentages, and SPSS version 23 was used to generate the mean and standard deviation while Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significant levels.

Results

The findings of the study are presented in the following tables with explanations:

Section A: Demographics Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1: Gender of the Respondents

Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Male	57	26
Female	160	74
Total	217	100

Table 1 shows that 160(74%) of the respondents were female while 57(26%) were male. This implies that majority of the respondents under study were female.

Table 2: Age Range of the Respondents

Age Range	Frequency	Percentage (%)
21-30	150	69
31-40	51	24
41-50	16	7
Total	217	100

Table 2 revealed that 150(69%) of the respondents were within the age bracket of 21-30years, 51(24%) were within the age bracket of 31-40years while 16(7%) were within the age bracket of 41-50years. This implies that the majority of the respondents were within the age bracket of 21-30years.

Table 3: Year of Study of the Respondents

Year of Study	Frequency	Percentage (%)
100	47	22
200	58	27
300	67	31
400	45	20
Total	217	100

Table 3 shows that 67(31%) were in 300 levels, 58(27%) were in 200 levels while 47(22%) and 45(20%) were in 100 and 400 levels respectively.

Research Question 1: To what extent are LIS undergraduates aware of YouTube as an educational resource?

Table 4: Extent to which LIS Undergraduates’ are Aware of YouTube

S/N	Extent to which LIS Undergraduates’ are Aware of YouTube	Very Often	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Mean	SD
1.	How aware are you that YouTube offers educational content related to LIS topics?	79	129	8	1	3.3	0.57
2.	To what extent are you aware that educational content on YouTube is freely available online for LIS students and the general public?	69	136	10	2	3.2	0.58
3.	How knowledgeable are you about the potential of educational YouTube videos to enhance your learning experience in LIS?	70	135	8	4	3.2	0.61
4.	How aware are you that educational YouTube videos can serve as a supplement to classroom lectures in your LIS studies?	60	139	17	1	3.1	0.58
5.	To what extent are you aware of the availability of educational content on YouTube in various courses or disciplines related to LIS?	48	140	23	6	3.0	0.66
	Grand Mean					3.2	0.6

Table 4, therefore shows that items 1-5 have mean values that are above the criterion mean (2.5). More so, the grand mean (3.2) is greater than the criterion mean (2.5), which shows that LIS undergraduates’ have a high extent of awareness concerning YouTube educational as an educational resource. The data suggests that LIS undergraduates are aware of the availability and benefits of educational videos on YouTube, and perceive them as valuable resources in their learning journey.

Research question 2: To what extent do LIS undergraduates utilize YouTube as an educational resource?

Table 5: Extent to which LIS Undergraduates’ Utilize YouTube

S/N	Extent to which LIS Undergraduates’ Utilize YouTube	Very Often	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Mean	SD
1.	How often do you use YouTube educational content to supplement your understanding of LIS topics?	69	136	10	2	3.2	0.58
2.	To what extent has watching YouTube videos related to LIS subjects enhanced your learning experience?	44	161	7	5	3.1	0.55
3.	How frequently do you find YouTube videos helpful in comprehending complex LIS concepts?	58	149	5	5	3.1	0.58
4.	To what extent has YouTube educational content contributed to improving your critical thinking skills in the field of LIS?	52	138	19	8	3.0	0.68
5.	How often do you prefer YouTube videos over traditional textbooks or articles for learning LIS concepts?	39	160	10	8	3.0	0.60
	Grand Mean					3.1	0.6

Table 5 shows that items 1-5 have mean values that are above the criterion mean (2.5). More so, the grand mean (3.1) is greater than the criterion mean (2.5), which shows that LIS undergraduates have a high extent of utilization of YouTube as an educational resource. These findings suggest that LIS undergraduates are actively leveraging YouTube as a learning resource, particularly for supplementing their understanding of course materials, enhancing their comprehension of complex concepts, and improving critical thinking skills among others.

Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between LIS undergraduates’ level of awareness and utilization of YouTube educational content

Table 7: Relationship between LIS Undergraduates’ Level of Awareness and Utilization of YouTube Educational Content

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	N	R	p-value	Remark
Awareness	13	2.3	217	0.675	0.023	Significant
Use	12	2.4				

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 7 shows the relationship between LIS undergraduates’ awareness and utilization of YouTube educational content. The table shows a positive correlation coefficient of 0.675 and a p-value of 0.023. Testing the hypothesis at 0.05, the p-value is less than the alpha value of 0.05. This means

that there is a significant relationship and the null hypothesis is therefore rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between LIS undergraduates' level of awareness and utilization of YouTube educational content in Delta State University, Abraka. The positive relationship implied that the level of awareness of YouTube educational content increases among LIS undergraduates, and their utilization of such content also tends to increase. In other words, students who are more aware of the educational content available on YouTube are more likely to utilize it in their learning.

Discussion

Research questions one and two revealed that LIS undergraduates have a high extent of awareness and utilization of YouTube educational as an educational resource. The high extent of awareness and utilization of YouTube as an educational resource is likely a reflection of the academic and professional expectations inherent in their field of study, as well as their orientation towards continuous learning and the effective use of information resources. This finding is in agreement with that of Okafor (2019) and Abdullah (2018) who found in their studies that students had medium-level awareness and extensively utilized YouTube educational videos. Lastly, the test of hypothesis shows there is a significant relationship between LIS undergraduates' level of awareness and utilization of YouTube as an educational resource in Delta State University, Abraka. The positive relationship implied that the level of awareness of YouTube as an educational resource increases among LIS undergraduates, their utilization of such content also tends to increase. In other words, students who are more aware of the educational content available on YouTube are more likely to utilize it in their learning.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings revealed that LIS undergraduates have a high extent of awareness, and utilization of YouTube as an educational resource. Lastly, the test of hypothesis shows there is a significant relationship between LIS undergraduates' level of awareness and utilization of YouTube as an educational resource at Delta State University, Abraka. Based on the findings, the researchers recommended promoting awareness, integrating YouTube as an educational resource into the curriculum, fostering critical evaluation skills, facilitating collaboration with content creators, and establishing mechanisms for continuous assessment and feedback. These recommendations aim to optimize the utilization of YouTube as an educational resource and enhance the learning experiences of LIS undergraduates in universities in Nigeria.

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